

Ionophoretic technique in the study of biologically important mixed complexes in solution (The system $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ -cystine-NTA)

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Abstract : In the present communication ionophoretic technique has been used for the study of Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} -cystine binary and Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} -cystine-NTA (nitrilotriacetic acid) mixed complexes. The stability constants of metal-cystine binary complexes are found to be $10^{7.80}$, $10^{6.90}$, $10^{5.10}$, $10^{4.66}$ and the stability constants of metal-cystine-NTA mixed complexes have been found to be $10^{5.18}$, $10^{4.88}$, $10^{4.76}$, $10^{4.10}$ for Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes respectively at $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (HClO_4) and 25°C .

Keywords : Binary complex, ternary complex, stability constant, ionophoretic technique.

Introduction

It is well known that the sulphur containing amino acids are of biological importance. The significance of these amino acids is enhanced by the fact, that they display important therapeutic activity¹. Their biological importance is attributed to the capabilities of the mercapto groups to undergo various complex formation processes. Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} are well known for their biomedical applications and play essential role in different physiological processes of the body²⁻⁶. Many transition metal amino acid complexes have considerable biological activity, such as antitumor properties. Amino acid usually increases the diffusibility of complex and enhances their biological action inside the cell. Such systems are widely used in the chemotherapy⁷. A number of metal-cystine complexes have been found to show antimicrobial activity⁸. Because of the importance of cystine and these metal ions, they have been chosen for the present study.

Results and discussion

Metal-cystine binary system :

Fig. 1 illustrates the relationship between absorbance differences and the pH's and thus gives an idea of the change of overall mobility of the metal ion species with change in hydrogen ion status of the system containing

Fig. 1. Relationship between absorbance difference and pH : (●) Fe^{III} , (■) Cu^{II} , (▲) Ni^{II} , (×) Co^{II} .

Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and cystine. A curve with a number of plateaus indicates the formation of certain complex species. A plateau is obviously an indication of a pH range where mobility is practically constant. The first plateau in each case corresponds to a region of pH where metal ions are uncomplexed. In this low pH region, the protonated form of cystine is maximum. Further increase in pH from this region onward which naturally leads to increase in ligating cystine anion concentration $[\text{L}^{2-}]$ and brings about a progressive decrease in overall ionic mobility of the metal ion species. This decrease indicates formation of complex of the metal ion with the ligand. A

point is reached beyond which mobility of the metal ion species remain constant regardless of the increase of pH of reaction mixture. This is the second plateau which corresponds to a pH region in which 1 : 1 complex is predominantly formed. One cystine anion combines with each metal ion to form : [Fe{OOC-CH(NH₂)CH₂-S-S-CH₂-(NH₂)CH-COO}]⁺, [Cu{OOC-CH(NH₂)CH₂-S-S-CH₂-(NH₂)CH-COO}], [Ni{OOC-CH(NH₂)CH₂-S-S-CH₂-(NH₂)CH-COO}], [Co{OOC-CH(NH₂)CH₂-S-S-CH₂-(NH₂)CH-COO}]⁻.

Complexes with Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} respectively. Regarding the coordination mode of cystine anion, it forms 1 : 1 binary complex. In this complex the geometry may be tetrahedral or square planar (coordination number 4) or octahedral (coordination number 6) in which four positions are satisfied by tetradentate cystine ion and others by solvent molecule (aqua group). A chelating structure for binary complexes with metal ions [Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II}] is shown as Fig. 2 in which cystine anion act as tetradentate ligand.

Fig. 2. Structure of binary complexes.

Beyond this plateau increase of pH has no effect and mobility remain constant.

The overall mobility *U* is a composite parameter contributed by different ionic species of the metal ion and is given by following equation :

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K_1 [L] + u_2 K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + \dots}{1 + K_1 [L] + K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + \dots} \quad (1)$$

where *K*'s are the stability constant of complexes and [L] is the concentration of cystine ion. *u*'s (*u*₀, *u*₁, *u*₂) are the ionic mobilities of different species of the metal ions which can be assessed from the plateaus of the figure. In the region between first and second plateau the system contains overwhelmingly a mixture of free metal ion and 1 : 1 complex. The existence of 1 : 2 complexes can be

excluded and hence the third term in the numerator and the denominator of the above equation can be justifiably neglected. *U* would be equal to (*u*₀ + *u*₁)/2 provided *K*₁[L] = 1.

Accordingly the pH corresponding to the average value of *u*₀ and *u*₁ is found from the figure and with the knowledge of the dissociation constant of cystine (p*k*₁ = 8.03 and p*k*₂ = 8.80)⁹, the concentration of cystine ion at this pH is calculated. Its reciprocal gives the stability constant *K* of the 1 : 1 complex. The concentration of chelating cystine anion [L²⁻] is determined as :

$$[L^{2-}] = \frac{[L_T]}{1 + k_1/[H] + k_2 k_1/[H]^2} \quad (2)$$

where [L_T] is the total concentration of the ligand cystine and *k*₁ and *k*₂ are the first and second dissociation constants of the cystine.

The equilibria for dissociation of the cystine may be given as :

Metal-cystine-nitilotriacetate mixed system :

Fig. 3 depicts the observation of studies carried out in M-cystine-NTA mixed complexes. These graphs clearly show the formation of two plateaus in each case. The first plateau corresponds to binary M-cystine complexes whereas the second plateau corresponds to the formation of new complex.

This new complex may be mixed complex of the type M-L-NTA or pure M-NTA complex. But with the help of related graphs of M-NTA complexes it was found that the absorbance difference in case of new complex is not

Fig. 3. Mobility curve. Metal-cystine-NTA system : (●) Fe^{III}, (■) Cu^{II}, (▲) Ni^{II}, (×) Co^{II}.

identical to M-NTA pure complex. Further this ternary complex has greater mobility than that of binary M-cystine complex hence these observations confirm the formation of mixed M-L-NTA complex.

Thus it is inferred that the mobility in the last plateau is due to coordination of the NTA anion to a 1 : 1 metal-cystine moiety resulting in the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed metal-cystine-NTA complex as,

For M-L-NTA complexes the stability constant K' is calculated by using modified equation.

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K' [\text{NTA}]}{1 + K' [\text{NTA}]} \quad (6)$$

Here u_0 and u_1 are the mobilities of M-L and M-L-NTA complexes.

From the Fig. 3 concentration of NTA at which overall mobility is the mean of the mobilities of the two plateaus is determined by using the equation.

$$[\text{L}^{3-}] = \frac{[\text{L}_T]}{1 + k_1/[\text{H}]} \quad (7)$$

The concentration of NTA anion $[\text{L}^{3-}]$ at pH 8.0 for this NTA concentration is calculated. K is obviously equal to $1/[\text{NTA}]$. All these values are also reported below and clearly indicate the superior coordinating power of NTA anion to other amino acid species.

The stability constant values for binary (M-L) and ternary (M-L-NTA) complexes are Fe^{III} (7.80, 5.18) > Cu^{II} (6.90, 4.88) > Ni^{II} (5.10, 4.76) > Co^{II} (4.66, 4.10)

which follows the Irving-William's¹⁰ order for the stability constants of transition metals of the first transition series. No comparison can be made as the literature values are not available.

Experimental

Instruments : Electrophoresis equipment from Systronic (Naroda, India) model 604 was used. It has a built in power supply (AC-DC) that is fed directly to an electrophoretic tube (18 cm long and 0.5 cm bore) with a stopper in the middle was fused perpendicularly at the ends with short wider tubes of 1.2 cm bore. This tube is kept in a thermostatic water bath at 25 °C. pH measurements were made with Century CP 901 digital pH meter using a glass electrode. The absorbance were measured with Spectrochem MK II (PEI) spectrophotometer. A Sico made constant temperature water bath has been used to ensure uniform temperature.

Ionophoresis set-up : (A) water bath, (B) electrophoresis supply, (C) support, (D) ionophoretic tube, (E) Pt electrodes, (F) stopper.

Chemicals : Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} perchlorate solutions were prepared by precipitating the corresponding carbonates from solution of chlorides (A.R. grade) with the solution of sodium carbonate, washing the precipitates thoroughly with boiling water and dissolving in a suitable amount of perchloric acid. The resulting solutions were heated to boiling on a water bath and then filtered. The solutions were standardized and diluted with distilled water as required. A.R. grade cystine, NaOH, HClO₄ and developing reagent for colour development

were used for specific colour development for different metal ions of binary system sets.

Electrolytic solutions : For binary systems 15 mL solution each containing $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, $0.1 M$ HClO_4 and $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ cystine was prepared at different pH values (by adding NaOH solution). In case of Fe^{III} , $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ Fe^{III} , $0.1 M$ HClO_4 and $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ cystine was used. For ternary systems the study was carried out by preparing sets of 15 mL solutions by progressive addition of secondary ligand NTA from $1 \times 10^{-6} M$ to $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ at a fixed pH 8.0 to a mixture of metal ion (having same concentration as in binary systems), $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ cystine and $0.1 M$ perchloric acid.

Procedure :

Metal-cystine binary system :

10 mL of electrolytic solution as mentioned for binary system is taken in an ionophoretic tube and then thermostated at 25°C . The position of the tube was adjusted in such a way that the level of the solution in one wide end arm reached a circular mark on it. This adjustment fixed the volume of the solution in both sides of the middle stopper. Two ($0.5 \text{ cm} \times 0.5 \text{ cm}$) platinum electrodes were dipped in each arm cup and a 50 V potential difference was applied between them. Electrolysis of the solution was allowed for 45 min, after which the middle stopper of the tube is closed. The solution of the anodic compartment was taken out in a 15 mL flask. The copper content of the solution was converted into copper thiocyanate¹¹. The volume was raised to a mark in the flask and the absorbance at 408 nm was measured with spectrophotometer. The Co^{II} content of the anodic compartment was converted into cobalt thiocyanate¹¹ complex and absorbance at 625 nm was measured after making up the volume to 15 mL. The Ni^{II} content was converted to nickel dimethylglyoximate¹² and absorbance was taken at 445 nm. Similarly the Fe^{III} content of the anodic compartment was converted to Fe thiocyanate¹² complex and absorbance was measured at 480 nm against a reagent blank. The same experiment is performed at different pH's and the observations are graphically represented in Fig. 1.

Metal-nitritotriacetate binary system :

The experiments for binary complexes of the Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} -NTA are prerequisite for the study of

metal-cystine-NTA ternary complexes. These studies have been carried out by Aziz¹³ and Singh^{14,15}. Their observations have been taken for comparison with our observations found in case of ternary complexes.

Metal-cystine-nitritotriacetate ternary system :

The study of mixed complexes was carried out by progressive addition of secondary ligand NTA from $1 \times 10^{-6} M$ to $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ at a fixed pH 8.0 to a mixture of metal ion (having same concentration as in binary systems), $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ cystine and $0.1 M$ perchloric acid. The reason behind keeping the reaction mixture at pH 8.0 is that much ahead of this pH the simple binary complexes of metal cystine and M-NTA are formed and remain intact even beyond this pH. The amount of secondary ligand NTA was increased each time in the ionophoretic tube and the electrolysis of the solution was allowed and its observations were recorded each time as it was done in case of binary complexes. These observations are graphically represented in Fig. 3.

A number of factors¹⁶ (e.g. diffusion, ionic strength and temperature) obviously vitiate the ionophoretic mobility of a particular ion. The technique described here is almost free of these vitiating factors and the reliability may vary to $\pm 2\%$.

As for the possibility of hydroxy compound formation, we had considered this aspect in our earlier studies. For this we performed the study of binary complex formation at two different concentrations of ligand giving complexing species at two different pH values. In that study we found two different plateaus but almost same stability constant. If it would have been a hydroxyl complex only one plateau at fixed pH value must have been formed irrespective of different concentration of ligand (cystine here) used. This clearly indicates that at very low concentration of metal (i.e. $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} = 10^{-4} M$) no hydroxy compound are formed. Hence the possibility of hydroxy compound formation at very low concentrations of metal ions is ignored in these studies.

Conclusions :

Thus ionophoretic technique used in the above studies proved to be very useful in studying the stepwise complexation in solution. The special electrophoretic tube which has been designed for this work, yields better results after standardization. This technique provides vivid

picturization of complex formation whose stability constant can be determined easily. Its further extension in the study of mixed complexation reactions is obviously an unique advancement in the realm of coordination chemistry.

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